

The suitability of using new digital payment system in the Inter-city
Transportation of Dhaka City : A study on Customers' Perspective

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Abbreviations

AML- Anti Money Laundering
CFT- Combating Financing of Terrorism
B2P- Business to Person
BB- Bangladesh Bank
BFIU- Bangladesh Financial Intelligence Unit
BEFTN- Bangladesh Electronic Funds Transfer Network
BRTC- Bangladesh Road Transport Corporation
DBBL- Dutch Bangla Bank Limited
DFS- Digital Financial Service
DPS- Digital Payment System
DTCA- Dhaka Transport Coordination Authority
FI- Financial Institution
G2P- Government to Person
IC- Integrated Circuit
MFS- Mobile Financial Service
MRT- Mass Rapid Transit
P2B- Person to Business
P2G- Person to Government
PSO- Payment Service Operator
PSP- Payment Service Provider
RFFO- Regulatory FinTech Facilitation Office

Abstract

This study aims to find the possibility of bringing a radical behavioral change in the payment practices in the transportation sector of the urban area of Dhaka city while ushering a new service arena for banks. The idea of a digital payment system through a virtual wallet is gaining trust even among the less literate section of the population. This action research puts light on the current popularity of cashless retail transactions in public transportations and takes a leap into the future possibility of digital payment in intra-city transport in the urban area of Bangladesh which is already present in some developed countries through vivid channels. Wilcoxon's paired signed rank test is used to detect behavioral change after simulating the respondents with the proposed digital payment system. The result shows significant statistical difference indicating that there is possibility of change in payment practices if this new digital payment system introduced in intra-city public transportation (Bus/Train) in Dhaka city. However, Most respondents seemed cynical about the ultimate success due to some factors – Tech Literacy Rate, Negative attitude of people towards change and ability of concerned parties to follow the process properly. The thoughts and expectations of the commuters of Dhaka city about a cashless payment system while roaming with bus/train are observed to extract prospects and challenges associated with it where banks can play a role to diversify their service. As the world is gradually moving towards digital financial services, this study tries to explore whether banks can foster financial inclusion by entering an undiscovered important service area of their regular lives.

Keywords: Digital Payment, Public Transport Payment, Financial Inclusion, PSP, PSO

Introduction

E- Banking has become the part and parcel of banking throughout the globe. Now, it is more of a must-have strategy for any bank than a mere luxurious investment. Banks in Bangladesh are going through an alarming condition of deposit crisis and revenue shortfall due to a convergence effect caused by the NBFIs and MFS companies. Professor Abdullah Al Mahmud (2022) suggested that the banks in operation should have been reaching out to newer customers and expanding the customer base. Unfortunately, all of them tend to run after a similar customer base. Rise of potential risk of losing market share and huge competition among banks are posing high threats of survival for new banks. To supplement those, Job shrinkages in banking sector is also a top concern among current bankers which had its harsh appearance during the peak of Covid-19 situation in Bangladesh. Banks are in dire need of exploring new market segments and new types of services if they want to keep their dominance in financial sector in the upcoming days. As the operational cost of having such venture is also a core issue, e-banking should be focused to curb the risks related to cost. Transactions through internet banking amounted to Tk 20,559 crore in December, up 154 per cent year-on-year and 21 per cent from that a month ago, showed data from the Bangladesh Bank. (AKM Zamir Uddin, 2022)

Public have embraced e-banking more than they did for manual banking. Banks are at the crossroads of the quests of minimization of operational costs and earning revenues from new sources. A big unexplored market of digital payment in transportation sector and retail shops can be a strong option to consider while offering new service to customers. Some MFS companies like Bkash and Nagad have already placed themselves as facilitators in retail shop payments. Some banks have POS systems to handle such type of payments in retail shops. But, by offering public to make transaction on mobile or smartphone has clearly addressed the need of customers prudently and thus, this has become a competitive vantage strategy for those MFS provider companies. Transportation and Retail shop purchasing are two most vibrant and needful sectors where most people must attend to lead their normal life. A digital payment system that can bring them ease and comfort while making payments for these services, can be a good source of income for banks.

Corporate moguls like Google, Amazon, and Alibaba group realized a core reality well ahead of others that to make customers dependent on them, they have to acknowledge every sort of need of that customer around the clock. No matter how many assets we hold, we must keep a certain amount of the portfolio liquid to maintain their day-to-day living. Banks in Bangladesh are facing a deposit crisis due to huge competition from other FIs and the sudden growth of MFS companies like Bkash and Nagad. Along with plastic money (Debit and Credit Cards), Some banks opted to compete with MFS providers bringing platforms like Cellfin (Islami Bank Bangladesh Ltd.), Rocket (Dutch Bangla Bank Ltd.), Upay (Union Bank Ltd.) to grab a portion in the huge volume of cash being transacted through digital wallets.

The challenge for reducing operational cost can be optimized through modernization of products and services while discovering new market segments showing a big potential. Even ten or fifteen

years back, terms like e-commerce payment, e-wallet, electronic money were not so popular in our country. But those have become unbreakable parts of our lives now. Banks have the infrastructure and institutional capabilities to promote services which can address financial needs of customers with efficiency.

1.1 Statement of the Problem

The highly ambitious dream of materializing Smart Bangladesh by 2040 and for transforming the “Digital Bangladesh” slogan into a true reality largely banks on adoption of cutting-edge technology and innovative system in delivering even the trivial amenities to citizens. A cashless society is no longer a high budgeted sci-fi imagination as human civilizations in developed countries are continuously transcending in digital payment realm ushering least developed and developing countries towards efficiency in payment system. Humans are always fascinated with finding solutions to perishability of their resources. A substitute product or service takes over where a practical solution is not available. Currency in cash form has always been a headache for government and financial institutions when it comes to preservation.

The world is moving gradually towards a cashless payment system amidst all the security risks and threats, and high dependence on technology and energy supply. We, the human race, are continuously struggling to make our lives easier and effortless despite all the backlashes of some cynics that this will eventually make us lazy, self-centered, and unhealthy. Thousands of years back, what a ruler barely could enjoy at his subordinates’ efforts, is now merely a trivial facility even a beggar can afford, a bliss of the compounding learning curve of civilization in terms of technology and knowledge. The payment system is an inevitable part of the survival of each human being. Thus, Corporate giants like Google have already converged to take a stake in the payments system exploiting the need of people to have a cashless society.

Paper-based cash management involves several distinctive issues –

- High dependency on paper and eventually on timbers and fibres which aggravate environment imbalance.
- Higher Cost of production and maintenance than digital currency.
- Humid Countries like Bangladesh have an additional issue of quick damage of paper currency notes due to prolonged monsoon and huge humidity in the air.

This study delves into the lives of people living in Dhaka to unearth the possibilities, if any, of introducing digital payment facility via mobile app in local transport (bus) which will enable customers pay the bus company directly from their respective bank accounts. The key issues this paper highlights are diversification of digital service offered by bank by penetrating a yet to be conquered segment of payment realm, reducing cash dependence for moving towards a cashless society and utilization of PSP/PSO to foster digital payment in urban life amenities.

1.2 Rationale of the study

It is a well-established fact that the two most important sectors people in Bangladesh spend cash money on a daily basis are Grocery shopping and transportation. Huge amount of cash is circulated on a daily basis in these two highly necessary activities which, without any doubt, amounts hundreds of crores only in urban area. Despite the presence of online grocery shops like Chaldal, Foodpanda or Daily shopping, people still prefer buying groceries in person from street vendors because service and groceries offered by the online stores are not up to their satisfaction and some want to save the extra bucks spent on delivery charge. The facility to buy groceries online and make payment through MFS still gives many people an alternative channel in case of emergency and saves their time and effort. But There is no alternative method of digital payment for Intra-city transportation via bus/train which circulates crores of taka each day. Ride sharing apps like Pathao, Uber etc. offers online payment service for rides around the city. But, the economic condition of most people does not allow them to afford those rides due to a high fare. For availing an intra-city mobilization by bus/train, one must carry paper currency.

To acclimatize with the ups and downs of economic cycle and volatile global political situation unveiling new economic threats, economists and scholars are focusing highly on diversification of service rather than going after the same clients (Mahmud, 2022).

The reasons why this study omits QR code payment system include, but not limit to-

1. Camera of mobile phone might not work properly
2. During crowd, some might not get to scan the QR properly which is quite a common phenomenon in our country.
3. QR code might not be properly detectable (e.g., for dirt, scratch).
4. To scan the QR while the bus or train is moving, there is a chance of hijacking or fall of the smartphone due to physical imbalance while someone holds their phone towards the QR code.

The reasons of not promoting card payment system in this study are-

1. Cards can easily be lost due to its size and shape.
2. Cards cannot show people the balance of their account. They ultimately will need a mobile phone to check whether the card needs to be recharged.
3. Most of the bus helpers/train ticket checkers of our country are not educated enough to maintain the POS machine let alone fix it instantly if it breaks down suddenly. A mobile app/USSD-based payment gives the full freedom and responsibility to customers for making such payment without any hassle.

This study includes USSD payment system along with mobile app payment system which is a revolutionary idea practiced by non-bank MFS Nagad and Bkash to give access to financial services like merchant payment to the less solvent segment of the society who cannot afford to avail a smartphone for mobile app payment.

Instead of focusing on a particular bank mobile app payment system, the system on one PSP/PSO mobile app/USSD system is highlighted for contactless payment. The rationale behind this approach is giving consumers more freedom of choice instead of compelling them to take service from a specific bank. A PSP/PSO platform e.g. ipay can facilitate a merchant payment from any bank card/non-bank MFS account.

1.3 The scope of the study

This study will only shed light on the probability of banks to stretch their service towards public transport payment in intra-city bus/train in Dhaka to enhance the scope of service-based income and liquidity solvency as their close competitor's digital payment service providers like Bkash, Nagad pose a threat to their business. Only the scenario of Dhaka city public transport (Bus) has been considered since penetrating a new market or partnering with a new industry is decided better only after implementing a pilot project taking one step at a time. Transportation payment through mobile app/internet banking for inter-city bus and train is already in practice. This research takes insights from that concept but does not fall under the scope of the study. Main focus, while analyzing the data, was given to public buses as most people in Dhaka city usually use it for intra-city transportation compared to train. However, advent of metro rail increased the usage of train for roaming around Dhaka city on a specified route. As the study highlights only the cash-based payment activity of public transportation, differences in other criteria of this sector were overlooked.

1.4 The Objectives of the study

The main objective of the research is to delve into the possibility of a new digital payment system in Intra-City transportation system (Bus/Train) through PSP/PSO mobile app/USSD system which is expected to reduce the dependence on paper currency. It also tries to explore prospects and challenges of banks playing a key role in such payment through PSP/PSOs. Another key objective of the study is gathering insights about the factors behind reluctance towards moving towards a cashless intra-city transport payment system and analyze some related cases around the world on bring a positive change about that tendency.

1.5 Methodology

The key focus while designing the process of data allocation and analysis was given on the relevance of the factors used to measure public trust in the proposed model based on established causalities (like having no quarrel with the bus conductor regarding getting the change back makes a man have less stress while traveling. One does not need to execute research to use this causality as there have been plenty of psychological papers discussing this cause-and-effect relationship between Quarrel and Stress).

A blend of both quantitative and qualitative perspective is used while collecting data required for this study. Survey questionnaire was used for data collection from sample respondents. Both primary and secondary source of data are used to gather information for this study from different journals, newspapers, survey reports, survey questionnaire and research papers.

For simulating the sample respondents, a hypothetical PSP/PSO company named "Transpay" is used in this research by demonstrating both app-based and USSD-based payment flowchart. The level of preference collected in this study is based on their reaction after this visual simulation. A five-point Likert scale was used to inquire about their overall experience with traditional payment system and new imaginary digital payment system in intra-city public transport system.

Sample respondents

The sample size was preferred to be 75 volunteers randomly selected from different social media and public places on the following criteria-

- Currently residing in Dhaka.
- User of Public Transport (Bus or Train).
- User of any Bank App or Bank run MFS service.

Figure-1.1 depicts the distribution of sample respondents on a map of Dhaka city. 40% of the respondents live around Mirpur, cantonment & surrounding areas and almost 33.33% of the sample resides near old Dhaka and surrounding locations.

Figure-1.1: Residence of the sample respondents in Dhaka City
Source: Author's Calculation

Hypotheses

Independent variable for this study is a mobile app/USSD based payment system for Intra-city transportation (Bus/Train) through PSP/PSO which might influence customers towards digital payment while transporting through Intra-city bus/train.

- **H0:** A mobile app or USSD based digital payment system for direct transfer of money from savings accounts to company account in Intra-City Public Transport (Bus) is not going to make any positive impact on the choice of payment of customers.
- **H1:** A mobile app or USSD based digital payment system for direct transfer of money from savings accounts to company account in Intra-City Public Transport (Bus) is going to positively influence the choice of payment of customers.

Literature Review and Conceptual Issues

This study being action research on public transport payment service in Intra-city transportation by bus/train has some relevance with the researches done on digital payment, public transport payment, IT readiness and security of banks, diversification of products and services by banks and digital services as part of financial inclusion. Since the start of MFS in 2011, Bangladesh experienced a continuous growth in number of account holders, volume and number of transactions in MFS (BMFSR,2022).

N. Delic and A. Vukasinovic presented a paper on IEEE conference held in Las Vegas in 2006 on how a symbiosis relationship between banks, application service providers and mobile network operators can benefit all of the stakeholders while providing digital financial service to their end users (Delic & Vukasinovic,2006). Herstatt et al., (2007) mentioned that digital payment denoted to provision and access to banking and financial services with the use of mobile telecommunication devices. The mobile platform offers a convenient method for managing money without handling cash. Mobile phone operators recognize M-banking as a potential service to offer to customers. On the other hand, banks and other financial institutions see M-banking as a catalyst to provide services to “the unbanked” (Maurer, 2008).

Fontes et al. (2017) conducted survey research funded by ERFD (European Regional Development Fund) which focused on the adoption of mobile payment system in public transport of Oporto and Beijing. A Mann Whitney and Kruskal-Wallis test were applied to detect any statistical difference among two or more sub-groups regarding their acceptance about mobile payment system in transport sector. The samples from Beijing showed that they were significantly motivated about the benefits of such payment facility in terms of convenience and saving time (Fontes et. al,2017).

While China and India currently lead the booming Asian FinTech scene, Bangladesh is making strides towards catching up. Government efforts like "Digital Bangladesh" and increasing internet and smartphone use are driving the adoption of financial technology. This is transforming the financial services industry, moving away from a uniform approach to offering customized solutions for individual needs. However, many financial innovations fail due to fundamental design flaws or being substituted by better alternatives. (Khan et. al,2020).

Global Findex Database Report,2021 shows that around 1.4 billion adults were unbanked throughout the world during 2021, of which, 4% lives in Bangladesh which amounts 2.85 crores of adult citizens. Figure-2.1 shows that nearly 50% people of Bangladesh were unbanked at the time of reporting but more than 69% of such unbanked population have access to mobile phones. Studies indicate mobile phones offer promising solutions to access challenges faced by unbanked individuals. Digital financial services can bridge the physical gap between banks and customers, especially in geographically dispersed regions. This is supported by high mobile phone ownership among unbanked adults who cite distance as a barrier. For instance, in Indonesia, 36% of unbanked adults struggle with distance, yet 55% of them own mobile phones. Similarly, in Cambodia, 35% lack access due to distance, yet 75% have mobile phones. This suggests digital financial services could be particularly impactful in such areas (Global Findex Database,2021).

Figure-2.1: Percentage of unbanked people in South Asia in terms of possessing a mobile phone. Source: Global Findex Database 2021; Gallup World Poll.

Regulatory Framework

The payments System of Bangladesh is highly regulated by Bangladesh Bank. Payment and settlement systems set the tools and boundaries by which funds are transferred among financial institutions, businesses, and individuals and are crucial for proper functioning of country's financial system. Beside applying new rules and regulations to foster payment systems innovation, Payments System Department (PSD) strives for promotion of new payments, clearing to ease financial transactions by maintaining circulation of money in the economy under the guidance of Bangladesh Bank Order, 1972. Additionally, the Payment Systems Department is responsible for issuing system rules, which outline the duties and obligations of participants within various payment systems. Presently, Bangladesh Bank is in the process of drafting the Payment and Settlement Systems Act, which is undergoing review at the Ministry of Finance (Bangladesh Bank, 2023).

Recognizing the benefits of innovation in fintech, the creation of a Regulatory FinTech Facilitation Office (RFFO) occurred in October 2019. This can be seen as a crucial initial move towards encouraging greater participation of financial sector innovators in the market, aiming to make financial services more accessible to the general public at affordable rates. The RFFO aids

interested innovators in the FinTech sector to submit their ideas for pilot projects and offers regulatory guidance to the participants (Bangladesh Bank,2023).

Bangladesh Mobile Financial Services (MFS) Regulations,2022 sets the laws which all parties involved must comply to create an enabling and competitive ambience to promote cost-efficient MFS. This also ensures access to affordable cost of fintech services to poor people and unbanked portion of the country. Complying with AML/CFT guidelines set by BFIU also falls under this regulation to tackle money laundering and terrorist financing. This newly adopted law also buttresses significant regulations set in the Bangladesh Payment and Settlement Systems Regulations, 2014. Current financial services allowed in Bangladesh by the aforementioned regulations are- Cash-In, Cash-Out, P2B payments, B2P payments like salary, P2P money transfer, B2B payments, online e-commerce payments, G2P and P2G payments and disbursement of foreign inward remittances. The proposed digital payment system for Intra-city transportation payment system falls under the P2B payments to merchant accounts. Essential qualities for reliable collaboration of MFS providers as set by BMFSR,2022 are:

- **Inclusiveness:** Agents from diverse backgrounds are welcome.
- **Expertise & experience:** Proven ability to handle the assigned role.
- **Financial stability:** No history of bankruptcy, sound business reputation.
- **Strong security:** Up-to-date security measures, regular audits, and clear reporting.
- **Resilience:** Can fulfill commitments even in challenging situations.
- **Clean record:** No criminal background declared.

MFS providers must adhere to the ICT Act, 2006 (amended in 2013) and the Guidelines on ICT Security for Scheduled Banks and Financial Institutions, 2010 issued by BB, in addressing ICT security issues in respect of MFS.

Findings and Data Analysis

3.1 Market Analysis

In Bangladesh, the financial industry is experiencing ongoing growth as it adapts to the changing demands of the expanding economy. The increasing number of mobile phone users, advancements in payment and financial systems leveraging IT infrastructure, widespread availability of mobile networks and internet access have all contributed to a surge in opportunities for improving Mobile Financial Services (MFS). These services aim to provide a convenient, cost-effective, and efficient payment method tailored to the needs of underserved, unbanked/underbanked, and low-income populations across the nation.

Figure-3.1: Growth of MFS accounts in last 5 years

Figure-3.1 shows the upward trend of MFS account number for last 5 years in Bangladesh. Around 16.05% increase in the total number MFS account was reported for last year compared to 2022. The account creation in rural area is much higher compared to urban area which is about 26.17% more. The reason behind this gap refers to fast business growth of non-bank MFS and less bank branches in remote areas of Bangladesh. The easy access to financial services has allowed many unbanked people to come under banking umbrella which is also reflected in the Global Findex Report,2021. Account ownership has risen from 31.74% in 2014 to 52.81% in 2021. However, calculating the percent change, we are behind Srilanka, India and Nepal. The growth is mostly credited to rise in mobile money account. Figure-3.2 depicts gradual increase in mobile money account in Bangladesh.

Figure-3.2: Gradual rise in mobile money account

Figure-3.3: Growth of MFS transactions in merchant payment in last 5 years

Figure-3.3 illustrates that there was a remarkable surge in MFS transactions for merchant payment in 2023 compared to past years which amounts about 83.36% growth compared to 2022. Overall, in last 5 years the growth in terms of transaction number was around 488.41% which is quite inspiring to give us hope about future potential towards a cashless society. Figure-3.3 shows a continuous rise in the amount of money mobilized through MFS channel. Last year, around Tk. 5426.8 crore was transacted to make payments to merchants using MFS. There was 61.51% rise compared to 2022. In last 5 years, the growth was nearly 914.15% which is an astounding progress

Figure-3.4: Growth in amount through MFS transactions in merchant payment in last 5 years

Overall, the positive trend of MFS account, transaction frequency and volume in terms of taka shows gradual popularity and public trust in digital financial service which marks a great potential for a digital payment system introduced in intra-city transportation in Dhaka city.

Currently, according to Dhaka's 20-year strategic transport plan (revised), people in and around Dhaka make more than 20 million trips a day. 64 per cent of these are done by buses (Hossain,2023). This amounts around 12.8 million trips per day. No dependable data was found on the people commuting by train inside Dhaka city. No bus takes any less fare than Tk.10 even for a 50-meter distance ride. The fare range of bus can be around Tk.10 up to Tk.100 approximately subject to distance travelled. Even if one-fourth of these passengers travelling by bus switch a mobile app/USSD based payment system, about Tk. 6 crore is being mobilized to bus companies bank accounts each workday with the support of PSP/PSO. This amount of money is currently being handled in cash which could be utilized by banks for meeting liquidity needs to run day-to-day business and invest in credit creation to boost up private sector investment. A sustainable cash inflow on a daily basis is vital for banks to maintain robust banking operation. During Covid-19 situation, it was a common scenario where people were bound to withdraw their savings in banks for survival which aggravated liquidity crisis in some banks. Public transport service is a basic need of people. Even in times of crisis, people need to move to work and educational institutions.

3.2 Stakeholder Analysis

The key stakeholders of this type of projects are Government bodies regulating public transportation (in this case, DTCA, BRTC, Concerned ministry), Bus owners, PSP/PSOs, Banks and other interested financial institutions and end users. The end users, financial institutions and payment facilitators hold low authority but high interest regarding this project. Regulatory bodies like RFFO and Payment systems department have the high authority to approve and regulate such management system. Bus owners also fall under the criteria of top stakeholder in terms of authority and power. There is tendency among them to show less income for the purpose of tax evasion. For this reason, resistance should be expected from their side and this can be resolved by Dhaka Transport Coordination Authority which has a high interest to give better service to end users. Being a government body, they also hold the authority to persuade any stakeholder to realize the positive impact of such projects. The end users/commuters hold the least authority although their high interest in such project spells the success or failure of it.

3.3 Analysis of Data Collected from Sample Respondents

3.3.1 Demographic Profile of the Respondents

This is needless to assert that social orientation based on gender or age, educational background, and socio-economic conditions are some subconsciously controlling factors to make people hold a positive or negative attitude towards a product or service.

Variables	Class	Frequency	Percentage (%) of Total
Age (in Years)	19-23	29	38.66%
	24-28	36	48.00%
	29-33	7	9.33%
	34-38	2	2.66%
	39-44	1	1.33%
Gender	Male	58	77.33%
	Female	17	22.67%
	Others	0	0%
Educational Status	Higher Secondary	11	14.66%
	Undergraduate	33	44.00%
	Graduate	21	28.00%
	Post Graduate	10	13.33%
Profession	Student	54	72.00%
	Govt. Employee	7	9.33%
	Pvt. Sector Employee	7	9.33%
	Contractual/Freelancing	7	9.33%
Monthly Income	<=10000	38	50.66%
	10001-20000	22	29.33%
	20001-30000	6	8%
	30001-40000	4	5.33%
	>=40000	5	6.66%

Table-3.1: Demographic profile of the respondents

Source: Author's Calculation

Most of the respondents fall in the age range of 19-28 years which shows that the research outcome will reflect the expectations and perspective of the future workforce segment of Dhaka city. From a socio-cultural point of view, male segment of our society travels by bus/train more compared to females which caused such high percentage difference in terms of gender among the respondents. Big portion of the respondents are undergraduate students or graduates. It is convenient for action research to get insights from a highly educated segment of the population. 72% of the respondents are students which partly is a harsh reflection of high unemployment and lack of formal job opportunities. In terms of income, around 80% people belong to lower to middle class range because transportation by bus/train is much affordable to them compared to other vehicles.

3.3.2 Preferred mode of Transport

Figure-3.5 illustrates that 83% of the total respondents prefer bus while roaming inside Dhaka city while train/metro rail is preferred by 17%. Bus is much suitable for passengers since railways are mainly used for inter-city transportation and metro rail MRT Line-06 only traverse along only a definite route of Uttara to Motijheel with fixed stations.

Figure-3.5: Most preferred mode of transportation among respondents while roaming in Dhaka City

Though the sitting arrangements and facility of bus is in abject condition, people with lower to mid-income range are bound to use bus to make their financial ends met. Apart from being shabby and unclean, buses in Dhaka do not offer adequate seating space for the passengers. Moreover, they take extra passengers for extra money making it more uncomfortable for the passengers. (Hossain, 2023)

Table-3.2 shows that Around 72% of the respondents has the facility of employer/educational institution hosted transportation service. Yet, around 40% of the respondents avail public buses/trains at least twice a day. 29.3% reported to use those transport mediums thrice on average daily where around 22% avail public transportation facilities for 4 to 6 times while roaming inside Dhaka city.

Number of Trips by bus/train per day		Frequency	Percent
Valid	1	6	8.0
	2	30	40.0
	3	22	29.3
	4	11	14.7
	5	5	6.7
	6	1	1.3
	Total	75	100.0

Table-3.2: Frequency of bus/train trips per day

Source: Author's Calculation

3.3.3 Money spent in public transport

A significant portion of household income low to middle class families in Bangladesh is spent on availing public transport facilities. Histogram in Figure-3.6 shows that the amount of money spent on public transport (Bus/Train) is not normally distributed or asymmetrical along the range. Most respondents spent around Tk. 500-1500 monthly for this purpose. The central tendency calculated in Table-3.3 shows that most people spent nearly Tk. 1950 on average for intra-city movement.

Figure-3.6: Histogram of expenditure on intra-city public transport (Bus/Train) per month

The Std. Deviation from the collected data is Tk. 1678.879 which denotes the expenditure needs in public transport sector is highly spread among the people in Dhaka city. It is mostly influenced by income levels of households, profession, age and gender. As most of the respondents are undergraduate and graduate students, their lack of job and availability of transport facilities offered by institution justifies the negative-skewness of the mean generated from the collected data.

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation	Skewness	
	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Std. Error
Per month expenditure on public transport	75	300	8000	1931.33	1678.879	1.610	.277
Valid N (listwise)	75						

Table-3.3: Descriptive statistics of expenditure on intra-city public transport (Bus/Train) per month
Source: Author's Calculation

3.3.4 Satisfaction level with current cash-based payment system

Current scenario of intra-city bus/train payment requires individuals to carry cash money in their wallet or purse. Whether it is liked or not, there is no alternative channel of payment for this transport segment. The respondents were asked to give their opinions on a 5-point likert scale about their current satisfaction level about cash-based public transport payment system in Dhaka city. 20% are highly unsatisfied and 37.3% feel somewhat unsatisfied. This 57.3% people will have less resistance for a change towards a cashless process offered to them. 21.3% of the respondents do not have any problem with current system nor do they feel satisfied with it. 20% of the respondents are somewhat satisfied. Only 1.3% said they are highly satisfied with current cash-based payment.

Level of Satisfaction with Current Payment System	Highly Unsatisfied (1)	Somewhat Unsatisfied (2)	Neutral (3)	Somewhat Satisfied (4)	Highly Satisfied (5)
Percentage	20% (15)	37.3% (28)	21.3% (16)	20% (15)	1.3% (1)

Table-3.4: Level of satisfaction in current cash-based payment system
Source: Author's Calculation

Figure-3.7: Histogram of level of satisfaction in current cash-based payment system

It is observable in Figure-3.7 that the distribution of data is quite normally distributed or symmetrical. The calculated mean is 2.45 which shows slight tendency towards less satisfaction regarding current cash-based payment system. The Std. deviation is 1.069 which is statistically significant for this data as level of satisfaction is an ordinal data and a difference of 1 indicates a complete shift to another level.

3.3.5 Preference level of the respondents after visual simulation of a hypothetical digital payment system for public transport

This proposed digital payment system offers easy P2B payment platform where a customer can easily make a payment with the help of his/her mobile phone. It would have the interoperability feature where customer with his/her bank/non-bank MFS account transfer the fare of public transport directly to the account of the company/organization operating that transport medium. Only 8% of the respondents highly disliked the proposed payment system. 14.7% thinks that this system is somewhat likely to fail to meet their expectations. 28% said they feel neither positive nor negative regarding this system. 21.3% people praised the new proposed system highly and said this would benefit their life style and they are willing to change their payment behavior if this is introduced properly.

Level of preference with new hypothetical payment system	Highly Unpreferable	Somewhat Unpreferable	Neutral	Somewhat Preferable	Highly Preferable
Percentage	8% (6)	14.7% (11)	28% (21)	28% (21)	21.3% (16)

Table-3.5: Level of preference for proposed mobile app/USSD based payment system
Source: Author's Calculation

Figure-3.8: Histogram of level of preference for current cash-based payment system

The bell curve in Figure-3.8 shows that the distribution of data is somewhat normally distributed or symmetrical. The calculated mean is 3.4 which shows slight tendency towards preference regarding new proposed digital payment system. The Std. deviation is 1.208 which is statistically significant referring that around 68% of the respondents are spread between these two categories- 2(Somewhat Unpreferable) and 5 (Highly Preferable).

3.3.6 Wilcoxon's matched-pair signed-rank Test

Wilcoxon's matched-pair signed-rank test is used to test any significant change on the same sample under different circumstances or independent variables. Such as- Product/Service testing by companies comparing with another product/service in the same market by having them tested by the same respondents. Since, The data gathered here is ranked data, Wilcoxon's matched-pair signed-rank test is the most suitable to detect any statistically significant change. Results of the Wilcoxon Signed-Rank test indicated that there is a significant large difference between Before ($Mdn = 2, n = 75$) and After ($Mdn = 3, n = 75$), $Z = 4.7, p < .001, r = 0.6$.

Parameter	Value
P-value	0.000003001
Surprisal (S-value)	18.3462
Effect Size (r)	0.6298
Z	4.6708
W, (W-, W+)	222.5, (222.5, 1317.5)
Number of pairs (N)	75
Non-zero difference pairs (n)	55
Ties Correction	529.875
S. E	117.1116
Average of differences (\bar{x}_d)	0.9467
SD of differences (S_d)	1.4786
Normality p-value	0.003092
Skewness	0.2229
Skewness Shape	Potentially Symmetrical (p-val=0.422)
Excess kurtosis	-0.4327
Kurtosis Shape	Potentially Mesokurtic , normal like tails (p-val=0.43)

Table-3.6: Wilcoxon's matched-pair signed-rank test calculation
Source: Author's Calculation

Because the data contains ties, equal differences ($C_{ties} = 529.875$), normal approximation was used.

1. Rejection of H_0 hypothesis

Since the $p\text{-value} < \alpha$, H_0 is rejected. The population's change is considered to be not equal to the expected change (0). In other words, the difference between the sample change and the expected change is big enough to be statistically significant. Thus, It infers that there will have a positive impact on payment behavior of Dhaka city dwellers in intra-city public transport system if the proposed digital payment system is introduced.

2. P-value

The p-value equals 0.000003001, ($P(x \leq 4.6708) = 1$). It means that the chance of type I error (rejecting a correct H_0) is small: 0.000003001 (0.0003%). The smaller the p-value the more it supports H_1 .

3. Test statistic

W can get values in the following range: [0, 1540]

$W_+ = 1317.5$, $W_+ \sim N(770, 117.1116^2)$.

The test statistic Z equals 4.6708, which is not in the 95% region of acceptance: [-1.96, 1.96].

4. Effect size

The observed effect size r is large, 0.63. This indicates that the magnitude of the difference between the mean ranks is large. The r value varies from 0 to close to 1. The rule for interpretation values for r normally is: 0.10 - < 0.3 (small effect), 0.30 - < 0.5 (moderate effect) and ≥ 0.5 (large effect).

The observed common language effect size is 0.14, this is the probability that a random value from Before is greater than a random value from After. This means that there is less probability of getting more satisfaction level in current cash-based payment compared to new digital payment system preference.

3.3.7 Issues concerned with cash-based payment

A digital payment system can solve many problems associated with current cash-based payment practice. A bar graph in Figure-3.8 illustrates that 88% of the respondents feel disturbed when they have to bargain with helpers/checker when they deny receiving authority approved fare and are misbehaved by them in that process. 60% do not like giving excess fare owing to any occasions/festivals/political turmoil/sudden informal price hike without government approval. A digital payment system would definitely eradicate any chance of happening this phenomenon. 54.70% believe that they feel mentally stressed for not having enough cash of small denomination while they have to make a payment. 53.30% thinks cash-based payment involves a risk of not getting the change back in case the helpers do not have enough of smaller value currency. 42.70% have the stress of getting torn notes as change or having helpers denying to accept their torn notes. 36% fear that carrying cash money makes them a lucrative target of hijackers/Thieves/Pickpockets/ Transgenders. 32% are concerned with getting affected by germs attached with paper currency. 22.70% feel anxious about the fact that paper currency can easily be torn, lost or destroyed compared to electronic money.

Figure-3.8: Issues concerned with cash-based payment in intra-city public transport

3.3.8 Advantages of the proposed system

There are some key advantages of the proposed digital payment system. 80% of the respondents think this will reduce the chance of bargaining with the helper/checkers. 70.70% are of the view that the worry to get change back will be gone. 61.30% are satisfied with the notion that there will be no hassle regarding getting torn notes while making payments. 57.30% support this system for its electronic money service which keeps no margin of getting fake notes. 54.70% of the respondents believe this will significantly reduce our dependence on cash money and the amount will be directly credited to the bank account of the company/organization of transport vehicles which eradicate the chance of employees working in this sector to misappropriate the revenue. 46.70% assumes that this will eventually reduce the cost of printing paper currency by government. Last but not the least, 42.70% expects that this system will reduce the chance of getting affected by the germs on paper currency as the payment process becomes contactless.

Figure-3.9: Advantages of proposed digital payment system in intra-city public transport

3.3.9 Challenges of proposed system from respondents' view

Although the proposed digital payment system is expected to reduce many shortcomings of traditional cash-based payment system, there are some challenges associated with this system. Figure-3.10 shows that 82.70% apprehends that such payment will depend highly on internet data package in mobile for app-based payment. They believe even if they purchase data package, the network service provided by operators is not qualified enough to provide a smooth service supporting this system. 42.70% found the system complicated compared to traditional cash-based system. 41.30% think having adequate charge in the battery of mobile phones would be a big issue for this system. 29.30% believe this will increase high dependence on electricity and technology, which a developing country like Bangladesh cannot afford to meet. 25.30% feel worried that not having enough money in bank a/c would jeopardize its objectives as crediting a bank account is not convenient while roaming. Only 1.3% of the respondents think that helpers/checkers will make lots of mistakes in such system and people would feel reluctant to shift to this payment system for their habit of using cash.

Figure-3.10: Challenges of proposed digital payment system in intra-city public transport

3.3.10 Jatri E-Ticketing Service: Innovation or digital eyewash

Jatri e-ticketing service in public buses was introduced to digitalize the ticketing process along with providing tech-enabled services through a connected system where bus owners gain real-time insights and streamlined operations, maximizing the potential of their vehicles (Daily Star,2023). It definitely helped commuters to tackle with inconsistent fares. Around 76% of the respondents experienced Jatri E-ticketing service. Table-3.7 shows that 46.70% of them preferred this system as it checks the helpers from taking excess fare.

Level of preference with Jatri E-Ticketing Service	Highly Unpreferable	Somewhat Unpreferable	Neutral	Somewhat Preferable	Highly Preferable
Percentage	10.70% (8)	13.3% (10)	29.3% (22)	32.00% (24)	14.7% (11)

Table-3.7: Challenges of proposed digital payment system in intra-city public transport

However, this system has some concerning drawbacks which ultimately compromise its objectives. To start with, it has used POS machines to give the owners a centralized data about revenues. But, when the printing paper depletes, the helpers cannot issue any ticket. If the machine breaks down for any reason, they do not have the necessary tech skills to fix those. There seems to be no actual supervision on the operation of this project. Most of the bus helpers usually do not use this system unless prompted by the commuters and often they bypass this system giving excuse of paper depletion or technological problems. On another point of view, this system is not cost efficient as it is adding an extra cost of the paper needed for ticketing and maintenance of the

machines. This can be overcome by a digital payment system where customers have the freedom to execute the payment while the bus/train operators will ensure the transaction done duly. Figure-3.11 shows some issues commonly faced by the respondents.

Figure-3.11: Issues of Jatri E-Ticketing System

3.3.11 Bank or Non-Bank MFS: From respondents' view

82.7% of the respondents have the idea that money kept to themselves lose its value each day. Banks and other FIs provide interests and share profit to customers who keep deposits or buys their shares. It is not like that the interest paid against deposits compensate for the value lost due to continuous inflation. But saving money in a bank at least gives a net positive return on that asset than keeping that amount to themselves idle.

Figure-3.12: Financial literacy about time value of money among respondents

		Frequency	Percent
Valid	0-5000	48	64%
	5001-10000	12	16%
	10001-15000	9	12%
	15001-20000	4	5.3%
	>20000	2	2.6%
	Total	75	100.0

Table-3.8: Amount of Cash money kept by respondents

Table-3.8 shows the amount of cash money kept by respondents to themselves. Almost 80% keeps cash money up to Tk.10,000 for payment purposes and emergency needs. Compared to the monthly income showed in Table-3.1, it is evident that most of the respondents keep a significant portion of their money in cash.

Figure-3.13: FIs/Mode of Investments where the respondents keep non-cash money

Figure-3.13 shows that around 82.70% respondents keep their non-cash money in bank accounts where their close competitor is non-bank MFS companies where 72% keep their non-cash money. The portion investing in Sanchaypatra, NBFIs assets or stocks of capital market is quite low among the respondents.

To compete with bKash and Nagad for liquid cash circulation and to promote digital financial services as per the guidelines of BB, Banks introduced mobile apps for customers to facilitate their seamless hassle-free access to financial services. Figure-3.14 shows the percentage of bank mobile app users of different banks. Two top banks preferred by most respondents are Islami Bank Bangladesh Limited and Dutch Bangla Bank Limited. Their success in reaching more people was made possible through MFS apps like “Cellfin” and “Rocket”.

Figure-3.14: Bank mobile apps used by respondents

Banks in Bangladesh attract deposits from customers mostly in the form of savings and FDR by providing 0.50%-9.00% subject to time and different conditions. On the other hand, non-bank MFS like bKash provides up to 3.0% interest on deposit biannually which requires at least 5000 tk. balance at the start of each month to be eligible for that. However, non-bank MFS does not charge any account maintenance. On the other hand, bank accounts come with comparatively more security but with high maintenance charge per year. The core difference lies in the business model of these two. Banks earn money mainly from credit creation but non-MFS earn their profits mainly from service charge and merchant fees. Banks also earn profit from service charge providing services to diversify business risks but it is not the main stream of income source for a bank. The business model of non-bank MFS is simple as it only serves the mobilization of money. However, Bkash, although being a sister concern of Brac Bank, partnered with The City Bank to launch nano loan within a limit of Tk. 500-20,000. They have already disbursed more than Tk. 175 crore out of which around Tk.125 crore is said to be recollected. (TBS,2023) The distinct feature of this nano loan is collateral-free nature although for being eligible, customers have to keep some money in balance and must make large numbers of money deposit along with making a certain number of payments.

Despite many backlashes against Bkash, Nagad and Rocket, they are getting more popularity for their availability on almost all roadsides through their agents. Within the year 2021 and 2022, Bkash made additional revenue of Tk. 636 crore making Tk.88 crore in profit in the year of 2023 (Habib, 2023). A newspaper report on bKash was shown to the respondents in the questionnaire which is attached in appendix-1. Nagad and Bkash are highly criticized for their lack of adequate control and regulation which is giving opportunities to money laundering and hundi (cross-border money transfer bypassing formal banking channels). Figure-3.15 highlights some issues which make respondents concerned about keeping money in non-bank MFS. However, Nagad has been licensed as a digital bank recently though it is not sure whether it will get involved in credit creation like a traditional bank do.

Figure-3.15: Respondents' concerns regarding keeping money in non-bank MFS

When respondents were asked of their preference about whether they would like to use bank accounts or non-bank MFS accounts for proposed digital payment system, Figure-3.16 shows that 54.70% preferred non-bank MFS accounts for this purpose due to ease of account management in this type of MFS companies.

Figure-3.16: Preferred mode for digital payment system in intra-city public transport

3.3.12 Drawbacks of banks for facilitating such payment system

Many respondents believe that e-banking system in banks is more complicated than their counterpart non-bank MFS companies. The regulations that a customer must go through for bank MFS account registration and authentication often require customers to visit branch of a bank where non-bank MFS kept it simpler in process with the help of their agents. Increase of agent banks can ease the process for customers but it might put pressure on the operational cost of a bank. Some of the respondents are doubtful about hidden charges as they sometimes found anomalies in their balance of their bank accounts. A key concern was recharging account whenever needed. Non-Bank MFS agents normally provide services from around 9 am to 10 pm on a daily basis. But a bank account user cannot do the same and all 11 bank MFS agents are not available like nagad and bKash. Some are of the view that non-bank MFS provide seamless transaction where they experienced some hiccups while making payments with bank MFS. People do not like to stand in a queue for minutes, fill a form and wait 1/2 working days for account creation in a bank. As the mobile app technology flourished, they are gradually demanding online account opening system which would save their time and energy significantly.

Recommendation from the respondents

Many respondents are of the view that mobile network service needs to be upgraded for such payment system. Ticket checkers and helpers should be trained accordingly to understand the transactions and cooperate the passengers in due manner. Some believe that non-banking MFS companies like bKash would be better than banks for such payment as recharging bank accounts is still lagging behind in terms of agent availability. The consumption of data should be kept minimum for such payment. The digital technology literacy is inadequate among city dwellers which might hamper its deliverables. This can be overcome by promoting digital transaction literacy on a large scale. Technological complexity should be kept minimum to make it more user-friendly. Some respondents welcomed this proposed system as an alternative channel to cash payment. Technical glitches and bugs in software need to be properly handled by authority to ensure smooth usage. Some of the respondents are a bit cynical about current technology level of the country who recommended for a better network infrastructure before implementing such project.

3.4 Case and Prospects Analysis

Case-01: Netherlands entering contactless transport payments system

Dutch public transport now accepts contactless payments like debit cards and digital wallets with the creation of OVpay. This nationwide system uses upgraded infrastructure and software for smooth travel and secure transactions. Mastercard partnered with local companies to implement the system and ensure compatibility with banks. Riders can easily tap-in and tap-out with their devices, eliminating the need for physical tickets. The system benefits both residents and tourists by improving efficiency, reducing congestion, and promoting sustainability. Subscriptions are still supported, but OVpay offers a convenient alternative for occasional riders. This innovative approach enhances overall livability within the Netherlands (Mastercard,2023). However, this kind of bank card-based payment is not suitable for a developing country like Bangladesh as most

people do not use debit/credit cards for payment. Rapid pass, an IC-based card is in vogue for contactless payment introduced in metroraill MRT line-06. But Most people do not issue a rapid pass despite 10% discount in fare to avoid the hassle of opening account with some specified DBBL branches and recollection fee of Tk. 200 if the card is lost/damaged. Most people use cash standing in a long queue to purchase a ticket.

Case-02: Pix Instant Payment of Brazil

Banco Central do Brasil (BCB) introduced Pix, the Brazilian instant payment scheme that facilitates its users - people, companies and governmental entities - to send or receive payment transfers in few seconds at any time, even on non-business days. Brazil’s recent experience with the Pix retail instant payment system shows hope for emerging economies struggling with payment cost. In little over a year since its launch in November 2020, Pix has signed up 67% of adults in Brazil, with free payments between individuals and low charges for merchants. Figure depicted the growth of pix. Pix's success boils down to two things: forcing big banks to join and giving the central bank both oversight and control (Duarte et. al, 2022)

Figure-3.17: Accelerating popularity of Pix Instant Payment of Brazil
Source: BIS Bulletin, 2022

Bangladesh Bank launched similar type of platform named ‘Binimoy’ last year based on the interoperability between MFS companies, Bank accounts and PSPs. It is still in pilot phase along with another platform named ‘Bangla QR’ which is expected to bring 70% of the population under cashless payment system. Same business model can be applied in case of this proposed intra-city public transportation where any passenger can pay the fare using only one platform irrespective of any bank account s/he uses.

Metrorail: Will it be a threat to the future revenue of public bus?

The bus owners in Dhaka city are facing challenges as they experience financial losses following the launch of metro rail services along the Mirpur and Abdullahpur routes in the capital. These owners are expressing frustration over the authorities' reluctance to permit route changes. Both parties agree that addressing the current situation requires an upgrade in bus services, replacing the outdated buses currently in operation. Presently, these buses are often observed with few passengers, many of whom are seated. Some commuters have voiced a preference for the metro rail due to its faster service, despite the higher cost compared to buses. While the minimum bus fare on these routes is Tk 10, the minimum fare for the metro rail is Tk 20. Mahbubur Rahman, managing director of Bikalpa Auto Service and organizing secretary of DRTOA, stated that since 2012, he has operated buses on the Mirpur 12–Motijheel route via Agargaon, Shahbagh, Press Club, and Gulistan. He mentioned a reduction in his fleet size, having sold some buses due to financial losses incurred after the recent introduction of metro rail services. Previously, he earned Tk 2,000–2,500 per bus daily, but with the metro service's introduction, his earnings have dropped to Tk 500–600 per bus (Akhter, 2024).

Although people are satisfied with a faster commuter service with metrorail MRT line-06. There are many reasons why this might not be a permanent solution for Dhaka city. Whenever the supply of coal is hampered aimed for electricity production, the electricity supply of the country gets hampered throughout the nation. As the service wholly depends on electricity, people would definitely need public buses in times of electricity crisis. Besides, in such an accelerating inflationary environment, the fare charged by this service is not budget-friendly to most people. In the time of emergency, this is, however, the best option for commuters for fast movement.

Padma Bridge: A new opportunity for market growth of Transport sector in Dhaka city

With a population of 22.2 million people in the urban area and 10.36 million in the city, Dhaka is one of the most densely populated cities in the world, with 47,400 people per square kilometer. (Populationstat,2022) Due to the completion of Padma bridge, the trade opportunities for southern districts with Dhaka city have increased. The commuter pressure has already been increased in Dhaka city owing to rising trade and commerce of products and services coming from southern portion of the country. This is likely to increase the pressure on public buses and trains offering intra-city public transportation which will boost their income with additional revenue.

Limitation of the Study

A big drawback of the study lies in the number of respondents. This is not large enough to jump to a conclusion whether the proposed service will benefit all the key stakeholders discussed. The data collected here to assess the level of preference for new digital payment system is not based on actual simulation but a visual one. An actual simulation has the possibility to generate a different result. A well user-friendly software built properly emulating genuine mobile app/USSD features would give a more positive response from people. This study is highly limited to customer perspective on the payment system of intra-city transportation. This is subject to further research on other relevant matters associated with such digital payment system which were ignored here. The use of QR code payment has started to flourish in Bangladesh. The success of such system against a mobile app/USSD based payment is subject to in-depth research with practical data which could not be studied in this research.

Conclusion

This type of digital payment system might not be available in near future in the intra-city transport sector in Bangladesh. But, the pace at which digital payment is gaining its fast acceleration and public trust along with technological innovation by corporate leaders to offer new payment services, contactless payment at every sphere of life can be achieved. Dependence on electricity and lack of proper maintenance of technology were seemed as prime barriers for moving towards a cashless society. Although the hypothesis testing in Wilcoxon's matched-pair signed-rank test shows that people might change their payment behavior in public transportation if such a digital payment gets introduced, such paradigm shift is subject to many technical factors managed by Banks, PSP/PSO and regulatory bodies. Government can plan policy measures by considering the possibility of transforming this untreated segment of paper currency into electronic money to promote financial inclusion by providing cost-effective digital financial service.

Bibliography

Harstatt, C., Buse, S., and Tiwari R. (2007), 'Mobile Services in Banking Sector: The Role of Innovative Business Solutions

Delic, N., & Vukasinovic, A. (2006). Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/4231731_Mobile_Payment_Solution_-_Symbiosis_Between_Banks_Application_Service_Providers_and_Mobile_Network_Operators

Maurer, B. (2008), 'Retail Electronic Payment System for Value Transfers in the Developing World', Department of Anthropology, University of California, California.

TBS. (2023, May 23). Bangladesh's first ever Digital Nano Loan: Customers availed Tk175cr through bKash app. *The Business Standard*. Dhaka. Retrieved from <https://www.tbsnews.net/economy/corporates/bangladeshs-first-ever-digital-nano-loan-customers-availed-tk175cr-through-bkash>

(N.d.). Retrieved from <https://www.bkash.com/en/help/interest-on-savings>

Akhter, S. (2024, February 10). City bus owners face loss for metro rail Bus service must improve, admit owners. *New Age*. Dhaka. Retrieved from <https://www.newagebd.net/article/225059/city-bus-owners-face-loss-for-metro-rail>

TBS. (2022, December 28). Passengers can also pay metro rail fare with Rapid Pass . *The Business Standard*. Retrieved from <https://www.tbsnews.net/bangladesh/transport/passengers-can-also-pay-metro-rail-fare-rapid-pass-559446>

Mahmud, A. A. (2022, March 11). Why open new banks if they chase the same customers? *The Business Standard*. Dhaka. Retrieved from <https://www.tbsnews.net/features/panorama/why-open-new-banks-if-they-chase-same-customers-383206>

Bangladesh Bank, R. (n.d.). Retrieved from <https://www.bb.org.bd/en/index.php/financialactivity/paysystems#legal>

Hossain, A. (2023, July 27). Dhaka public transport: How long dilapidated buses will ply. *Prothom Alo*. Dhaka. Retrieved from <https://en.prothomalo.com/bangladesh/yw5ec1xcda>

Mastercard. (2023). The Netherlands becomes first country to launch fully contactless public transport payments system nationwide. Retrieved from <https://www.mastercard.com/news/europe/en/newsroom/press-releases/en/2023/netherlands-contactless-transit-payments-system/>

Fontes, T., Costa, V., Ferreira, M. C., Shengxiao, L., Zhao, P., & Dias, T. G. (2017). Mobile payments adoption in public transport. *Transportation Research Procedia*, 24, 410–417. doi: 10.1016/j.trpro.2017.05.093

Khan, S. U., & Hasan, F. (2020). FinTech and RegTech: Possible Impact on Banking Systems in Bangladesh. *A Compilation of Keynote Papers of Roundtable Discussions of BIBM-2019*, 295–296.

Demirgüç-Kunt, A., Klapper, L., Singer, D., & Ansar, S. (2022). (tech.). *The Global Findex Database 2021: Financial Inclusion, Digital Payments, and Resilience in the Age of COVID-19*. World Bank Group. Retrieved from <https://www.worldbank.org/en/publication/globalfindex/Report>

Dhaka, Bangladesh population. (n.d.). Retrieved from <https://populationstat.com/bangladesh/dhaka>

Bangladesh Bank, (2018), ‘Bangladesh Mobile Financial services (MFS) Regulations’, available at: <http://bb.orgbbd/mediaroom/circulars/psd/jul302018psdl04e.pdf>, assessed on October 05, 2023.

Appendix -1: Questionnaire

Name-
Email-

Last Academic Qualification-
Age-

Gender-

1. Monthly Income
2. Current Location at Dhaka
3. Profession
4. Currently, which of the following public transport vehicles is more preferable to you while you are roaming inside the city?
5. Does your employer/educational institute provide transport facilities for workdays?
6. How many times do you need to avail public transport in a day?
7. How much do you spend on public transport(bus/train) per month?
8. How much satisfied are you with current cash-based payment system in public transport while roaming in Dhaka?
9. Which of the following Issues are concerning to you while making payments in cash while travelling Bus or Train in Dhaka City?
10. Please see the images given below of two models of proposed digital Payment system for Bus and Trains while roaming in Dhaka City.

Step-1

Step-2

Step-3

Step-4

Give your opinion about using this method for payment instead of cash payment. Do consider the risks of Cash Payment and QR payment introduced in some countries, Compare and then Answer.

Risks of Cash Payment:

1. Bargaining with Checker/Helper when they deny taking approved fare and being misbehaved by them
2. Getting Back Torn Currency Notes as change or Helpers denying receiving your torn notes
3. Giving extra money due to occasions/Festivals/political turmoil/informal price hike
4. Hijack by Thieves/Pickpockets/Transgender
5. Risk of carrying Fake Notes and getting that identified while making payment
6. Currency Notes carries lots of germs which can make you sick
7. Cash can easily be destroyed, torn or lost
8. Not getting change as helper/checker does not have enough cash of smaller value
9. Mental stress to carry enough notes of tk.2,5,10,20 or coins to avoid the risk of not getting your change back

#Problems of QR code Payment introduced in some countries' transport payment:

1. camera might not work properly
2. During crowd, some might not get to scan the QR properly.
3. QR code might not be properly detectable (e.g., for dirt, scratch)
4. To scan the QR while the bus or train is moving, there is a chance of hijacking or fall of the smartphone due to physical imbalance while someone holds their phone towards the QR code.

11. What challenges do you think would hamper the proper functioning of this payment system?
12. What following benefits do you think will be realized if the proposed digital payment system is introduced?
13. Have you recently experienced E-Ticketing System in buses introduced by Jatri Ltd.? If you answered Q17 Yes, how much satisfied are you with the changed E-Ticket System? If you answered No, Ignore this question.
14. If you answered Q17 Yes, which of the following issues seem concerning to you while having this e-ticket service of Jatri Ltd.? If you answered No, Ignore this question.
15. Are you aware of the fact that your money which you hold in cash loses its value if it isn't kept in a bank or invested elsewhere in the form of real asset or financial asset?
16. How much cash money do you usually keep to yourself per month?
17. Where do you usually keep your money which are not in paper currency (meaning: the cash money you keep with yourself or at home which is always ready for transaction without getting any financial institution involved)?

18. Which of the followings are concerning issues to you involved in keeping money in Non-Banking Mobile Financial Service Companies?

হুন্ডি পাচারে বিকাশের সম্পৃক্ততা

- MFS (Bkash, Nagad) are the prime target of scammers due to easy transaction method and less secured than bank transactions
 - Many MFS agents were arrested by police for being involved with money laundering
 - They charge more amount for money withdrawal than banks do
 - Regulation of MFS by central bank is inadequate compared to banks in terms of accountability of their business
19. If a payment service provider introduces a digital platform for payment in Intra-city Transport (Bus and Train), which option seems more practical and favorable to you?
- Bank Account
 - Non-Bank MFS accounts
20. If you answered MFS in the Q24, give suggestions on how banks can improve their service for this type of payment. If you answered bank ac, write n/a
21. Write the name of the bank app which you currently use for digital payment. If the number is more than one, write the name of most used app along with its bank name.
22. Give any recommendations/ comment on this digital payment model proposed for Intracity Public transport (Bus/Train).